

Exact spectral calculations of wave-induced ship responses considering arbitrary speed-heading combinations in short-crested waves

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Abstract. This paper introduces an algorithm for spectral calculations of wave-induced responses of a ship sailing in short-crested, multi-directional waves at non-zero forward speed. The algorithm computes the response spectrum, in the ship-frame of reference, using a given directional wave spectrum and transfer functions. Validation is achieved by comparing the encounter-domain spectrum of a response with the true spectrum derived from FFT analysis of the response time series. The algorithm performs well, but achieving a perfect match between the spectra requires high resolution of vectors representing encounter and absolute frequencies, as well as relative wave heading. Additionally, a careful selection of cut-off frequency-values is crucial. Above all, for comparable accuracy between time series simulations and spectral calculations, required CPU time can be drastically reduced, $\mathcal{O}(1\text{day})$ and $\mathcal{O}(1\text{s})$, respectively.

Key words: *Spectral calculations; Ship responses; Short-crested waves; Doppler shift*

1. Introduction

Wave-induced ship responses are often calculated using linear theory, which allows for spectral calculations through frequency domain transfer functions and wave spectra. These calculations are fast and statistically accurate.

Spectral calculations are used in various applications, including early-stage ship design for seakeeping evaluations [1], real-time shipboard decision support [2, 3, 4, 5], post-voyage performance assessment with digital twins [6, 7, 8, 9], and wave buoy analogies [10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15]. Simple forms of these calculations assume long-crested, uni-directional waves and head sea conditions. Sometimes, only statistical variances are needed, derived from pseudo (non-measurable) spectra computed in the absolute domain. However, generally, the calculations must account for short-crested, multi-directional sea conditions, when the detailed response spectrum, as actually *encountered* by the advancing ship, is wanted. The relative velocity and the angle between the vessel and waves determine the observed wave period, described by the Doppler shift, which maps absolute frequency to encounter frequency. This mapping is particularly delicate in spectral calculations for waves from abaft beam. At this point, suffice to copy, somewhat discouraging, a remark from one of the classic textbooks [16]: “As a practical matter, the complications [of spectral calculations] are such that estimates of the response spectrum in short-crested seas are virtually never done, and the interested reader is referred to St. Denis and Pierson (1953), or Price and Bishop (1974) for further details.”, noticing that the suggested references¹ do *not* include practical details related to actual calculations of a response spectrum.

1.1 Objective and content

In this paper, we discuss an algorithm developed for making spectral calculations of wave-induced responses of a ship sailing in short-crested waves at arbitrary wave-encounter angles at any forward speed.

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¹The two references (i.e., St. Denis and Pierson, 1953; Price and Bishop, 1974) appear as [17] and [18], respectively, in the list of references.

We show that the algorithm, with any desired accuracy from an engineering viewpoint, can reproduce the results obtained from time series simulations representing a ground truth. However, the investigations reveal that the resolution of the vectors of frequency (absolute *and* encounter) and wave-encounter angle must be high, if a *perfect* match between the spectral calculation and the ground truth is wanted. The paper is a condensation of [19], in which the actual algorithm is detailed, and the paper contains the key findings of the original study, although the calculations refer to a different ship and a different response compared to [19].

In the next section, Section 2., the theoretical foundation and the associated methods are detailed. In addition, Section 2. includes an example that highlights the practical problem occurring when spectral calculations in the encounter domain are performed. While the details of the numerical algorithm are given by [19], Section 3. includes a pseudo algorithm and a few remarks introducing the computational procedure. The algorithm is tested and validated through a case study involving the heave response of a ship sailing in short-crested waves, as described in Section 4.. Results and discussions of the case study are presented in Section 5., and final remarks are given in Section 6..

2. Theory and fundamentals

2.1 Doppler shift

At (non-zero) forward speed, a ship meets waves at the encounter frequency ω_e . The encounter frequency is related to the absolute wave frequency ω_0 via the Doppler shift. In deep-water waves, the Doppler shift reads [20]

$$\omega_e = |\omega_0 - \omega_0^2 \psi|, \quad \psi = \frac{U}{g} \cos \beta \quad (1)$$

where U is the forward speed, g the acceleration of gravity, and β is the relative wave heading, i.e., the angle between the velocity vector of the ship and the direction of the propagating waves, meaning that $\beta = 180^\circ$ is head waves. We also note that the frequency of encounter is always positive, which explains why the absolute value is used. While the consequence of the Doppler shift is trivial from a mathematical point of view, the practical implication in connection with implementations is not straightforward [16, 20, 21, 22], since for waves from abaft beam, i.e. $\beta \in [0^\circ - 90^\circ[$ or $\beta \in]270^\circ - 360^\circ]$, any encounter frequency can be the result of up to three absolute frequencies. The particular situation is illustrated in Figure 1, where $U > 0$ and following waves ($\beta = 0^\circ$) are assumed. Solving Eq. (1) for ω_0 , when $\omega_e < 1/(4\psi)$, the values of the

Figure 1: The relationship between encounter wave frequencies and absolute wave frequencies is governed by the Doppler shift leading to a parabola in waves from abaft beam. If ω_0 is solved for ω_e , up to three solutions need to be considered, stressing that only positive values of ω_e exist. Note that $\psi = U/g \cos \beta$.

set of absolute frequencies corresponding to the same encounter frequency ω_e are:

$$\omega_{0,1} = \frac{1 - \sqrt{1 - 4\psi\omega_e}}{2\psi} \quad (\text{Region I}) \quad (2a)$$

$$\omega_{0,2} = \frac{1 + \sqrt{1 - 4\psi\omega_e}}{2\psi} \quad (\text{Region II}) \quad (2b)$$

$$\omega_{0,3} = \frac{1 + \sqrt{1 + 4\psi\omega_e}}{2\psi} \quad (\text{Region III}) \quad (2c)$$

2.2 Spectrum representation of ship motions

Here, the most general situation is considered and the waves are modelled from a short-crested sea state characterised by a directional wave spectrum $E(\omega_0, \nu)$ with waves propagating *from* the compass direction ν . The wave spectrum may be obtained from measured data (buoy, ship, etc.), via a spectral wave model, or it may be obtained from a theoretical, idealised spectrum. In the present study, the origin of the wave spectrum is of no importance.

In a seaway, characterised by the directional wave spectrum $E(\omega_0, \nu)$, the spectrum $R(\omega_e)$ of a wave-induced response (e.g., any of the six DOF motions) of a ship sailing at speed U is in schematic form,

$$R(\omega_e) = \int_0^{2\pi} |\Phi_R(\omega_e, \beta)|^2 E_e(\omega_e, \nu) d\nu \quad (3a)$$

$$\beta = \pi - (\chi - \nu) \quad (3b)$$

$$\omega_e = |\omega_0 - \omega_0^2 \psi| \quad (3c)$$

$$E_e(\omega_e, \nu) = \left\langle E(\omega_0, \nu) \frac{d\omega_0}{d\omega_e} \right\rangle_{\omega_e} \quad (3d)$$

$$\Phi_R(\omega_e, \beta) = \langle \Phi_R(\omega_0, \beta) \rangle_{\omega_e} \quad (3e)$$

where $\beta = \pi - (\chi - \nu)$ [rad] is the relative wave heading when the compass heading of the ship is χ . Equation (3d) is obtained by rewriting the equivalence between the energy in the absolute and the encounter domains, requiring the derivative $\frac{d\omega_0}{d\omega_e}$.

It is important to stress that the goal is to compute the response spectrum for an advancing ship, which means that ω_e is the independent variable. In other words, the Doppler shift needs to be solved "backwards" for establishing the corresponding absolute frequency that, in turn, is needed when invoking the directional wave spectrum as well as the transfer function. Therefore, the angle brackets $\langle \cdot \cdot \cdot \rangle_{\omega_e}$, with ω_e as index, are used to emphasise that evaluation happens for a *given* frequency of encounter.

As already indicated, up to three absolute frequencies exist for waves from abaft beam for a given encounter frequency with reference to Eqs. (2a)-(2c), and the corresponding derivatives are:

$$\frac{d\omega_{0,1}}{d\omega_e} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - 4\psi\omega_e}} \quad (4a)$$

$$\frac{d\omega_{0,2}}{d\omega_e} = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - 4\psi\omega_e}} \quad (4b)$$

$$\frac{d\omega_{0,3}}{d\omega_e} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + 4\psi\omega_e}} \quad (4c)$$

The overall implication of the preceding is that two fundamental cases must be considered separately in the evaluation of equations (3a)-(3e): (1) Waves forward of beam, including beam waves, and (2) waves from abaft beam. The consideration of (1) is trivial, as a 1-to-1 relationship exists between absolute and encounter frequency, and this situation will not be discussed further. In waves from abaft beam, on the other hand, it is inferred that three distinct energy densities from the wave spectrum at $\omega_{0,1}$, $\omega_{0,2}$, and $\omega_{0,3}$, respectively, contribute to the encounter-response spectrum at ω_e , when $\omega_e < \frac{1}{4\psi}$. In general, for any given ω_e and waves

from abaft beam, the theoretical response spectrum should therefore be computed by,

$$R(\omega_e) = \begin{cases} \sum_{i=1}^3 \left[\int_0^{2\pi} \left\langle |\Phi_R(\omega_{0,i}, \beta)|^2 E(\omega_{0,i}, \nu) \left| \frac{d\omega_{0,i}}{d\omega_e} \right| \right\rangle_{\omega_e} d\nu \right], & \omega_e < \frac{1}{4\psi} \\ \sum_{i=2}^3 \left[\int_0^{2\pi} \left\langle |\Phi_R(\omega_{0,i}, \beta)|^2 E(\omega_{0,i}, \nu) \left| \frac{d\omega_{0,i}}{d\omega_e} \right| \right\rangle_{\omega_e} d\nu \right], & \omega_e = \frac{1}{4\psi} \\ \int_0^{2\pi} \left\langle |\Phi_R(\omega_{0,3}, \beta)|^2 E(\omega_{0,3}, \nu) \left| \frac{d\omega_{0,3}}{d\omega_e} \right| \right\rangle_{\omega_e} d\nu, & \omega_e > \frac{1}{4\psi} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

It should be observed that the magnitude (i.e., absolute value) of the derivative is used to ensure positive values only of the spectrum, realising that the derivative is negative in Region II. Strictly, using the magnitude of the derivative follows since an ordered range (low to high values) of encounter frequencies is considered, alluding also to the point that the independent variable is the encounter frequency (and *not* the absolute frequency). Additional remarks follow in Subsection 2.4. The precise implementation of Eq. (5) is detailed in [19] which contains a complete numerical recipe, directly programmable. On the other hand, Section 3. includes a pseudo code and a few practical aspects related to the implementation of Eq. (5).

2.3 Time series of ship motions

In linear theory, time series of measured wave-induced responses of a ship sailing with speed U can be simulated in accordance with [17]. In the particular case of a response $\rho(t)$, where t is time, the response is [23, 4]:

$$\rho(t) = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{l=1}^L [u_{l,n} c_{l,n}(t) + \bar{u}_{l,n} \bar{c}_{l,n}(t)] \quad (6)$$

where $u_{l,n}$ and $\bar{u}_{l,n}$ are uncorrelated, standard normal distributed variables, thus ensuring a Gaussian process, with zero mean. The resolution of the discrete vectors of frequency and wave direction is controlled by the indices n and l , respectively, and their corresponding upper values N and L . The deterministic coefficients $c_{l,n}(t)$ and $\bar{c}_{l,n}(t)$ are given by

$$c_{l,n}(t) = \sigma_{l,n} |\Phi_R(\omega_{0,n}, \beta_l)| \cos(\omega_{e,n} t + \epsilon_{l,n}) \quad (7a)$$

$$\bar{c}_{l,n}(t) = -\sigma_{l,n} |\Phi_R(\omega_{0,n}, \beta_l)| \sin(\omega_{e,n} t + \epsilon_{l,n}) \quad (7b)$$

$$\omega_{e,n} = |\omega_{0,n} - \omega_{0,n}^2 \psi| \quad (7c)$$

$$\sigma_{l,n}^2 = E(\omega_{0,n}, \nu_l) \Delta \omega_{0,n} \Delta \nu \quad (7d)$$

$$\epsilon_{l,n} = \arctan \left(\frac{\text{Im}[\Phi_R(\omega_{0,n}, \beta_l)]}{\text{Re}[\Phi_R(\omega_{0,n}, \beta_l)]} \right) \quad (7e)$$

where the requirement of energy equivalence, i.e., $E(\omega_e, \nu) d\omega_e \Delta \nu \equiv E(\omega_0, \nu) d\omega_0 \Delta \nu$, has been introduced in Eq. (7d). In addition, note that the resolution of wave direction (ν) and relative wave heading (β) is assumed to be identical for convenience to avoid the need for interpolation.

A main difference between time series simulation, on one side, and a spectral calculation, on the other side, of wave-induced responses, considering a ship advancing in a seaway, is that the absolute frequency can be used as the given frequency (i.e., it is the "starting point") in the time series simulation. Here, we note that the Doppler shift uniquely identifies a single encounter frequency for any given absolute frequency, all relative wave directions considered, i.e. $\beta \in [0^\circ - 360^\circ]$, and there are no ambiguities nor practical complexities in time series simulations using Eq. (6). Thus, from a predefined set of discrete absolute frequencies, $\omega_{0,n}$, $n = 1, \dots, N$ the corresponding set of encounter frequencies $\omega_{e,n}$ is also defined, and the computation of Eq. (6) can readily be made, when the wave direction and the relative wave heading have been discretised into $l = 1, \dots, L$ components, spaced uniformly on the interval $[0^\circ - 360^\circ]$.

2.4 Example: The faced *practical* problem

Returning to spectral calculation in the frequency domain, it seems tempting to start from the absolute frequency. However, deriving the frequency of encounter from the Doppler shift makes it impractical to compare spectra of measured data and theoretical calculations. This issue has been discussed initially by [24], and the plots in Figures 2 and 3 show the "controversy". Figure 2 is based on a spectral calculation where the starting point is a given set of absolute frequencies ω_0 used to calculate the (absolute) wave spectrum $E_0(\omega_0)$. The *transformation* of this spectrum to encounter domain, as observed from a ship advancing at 10 knots in stern-quartering waves ($\beta = 30^\circ$), is directly obtained from $E_e(\omega_e) = E_0(\omega_0) \frac{d\omega_0}{d\omega_e}$ using

$$\omega_e = \omega_0 - \omega_0^2 \psi \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{d\omega_0}{d\omega_e} = \frac{1}{1 - 2\omega_0 \psi} \quad (9)$$

Indeed, Figure 2 and its caption inform how the encountered wave spectrum is 'distorted' in stern-quartering waves, where three points are noteworthy: (1) the occurrence of negative spectral ordinates, (2) multiple spectral ordinates at some encounter frequencies, (3) the singularity at $\omega_0 = \frac{1}{2\psi}$, equivalently, $\omega_e = \frac{1}{4\psi}$. The observation (2) of multiple values at some frequencies is because of the Doppler shift that results in a non-ordered set of encounter frequencies for an ordered set (lowest to highest) of absolute frequencies. Consequently, the difference term $d\omega_e$ will not only attain positive but also negative values for a corresponding ω_e -vector. The observation (1) of negative spectral ordinates is thus related to the non-ordered set of encounter frequencies; emphasising that a negative ordinate (i.e., energy *density*) is *not* equivalent to the energy being negative. This is so exactly because the frequency derivative, $\frac{d\omega_e}{d\omega_0}$, will also be negative, so that energy itself is positive; since energy is the product of the spectral ordinate and the frequency derivative. Altogether, the (encounter) spectrum shown in Fig. 2 is 'mathematically consistent' and the spectrum can be used directly when/if transformation (back) to the absolute domain is carried out from $E_0(\omega_0) = E_e(\omega_e) \frac{d\omega_e}{d\omega_0} = E_e(\omega_e)(1 - 2\omega_0 \psi)$; but, it is stressed that a transformation is valid only for the initial pre-specified (and ordered) set of absolute frequencies ω_0 with a specific, but non-ordered, corresponding set of encounter frequencies ω_e .

The situation is different when *corresponding* time history measurements are observed and, as a post-process, analysed by spectral analysis (e.g., via FFT). In this case, the set of (observed) encounter frequencies will be strictly ordered (lowest to highest) and, as a result, the encounter spectral ordinates take positive values exclusively. This is confirmed in Figure 3 that shows the encountered wave spectrum, corresponding to the previous situation, cf. Figure 2, but derived from FFT of a time series. Evidently, it will be an uneasy task to match the two encounter-domain wave spectra (Fig. 2 vs. Fig. 3), although the two spectra are theoretically consistent. Another point would be that simulation of time series, generally, requires the study

Figure 2: Transformation of Bretschneider spectrum in stern-quartering sea ($H_s = 3.0$ m, $T_z = 8.0$ s, $\beta = 30^\circ$) leads to a heavily distorted encounter spectrum. The vessel speed is 10 knots. Note that the frequency axis represents both ω_0 and ω_e . Note that absolute and encountered spectra, E_0 and E_e , carry indices ($_0$ and $_e$, respectively) for emphasis. From [19].

Figure 3: A measured (i.e. simulated) wave elevation record (smaller plot in the right-hand corner) transforms to an energy spectrum having only positive ordinates at a strictly ordered set of encounter frequencies. Note that the frequency axis represents both ω_0 and ω_e . From [19].

of more than a single (short-time) realisation to achieve statistically representative results, as also discussed in connection with the case study, cf. Subsection 4.3.

3. Pseudo code

The appropriate way to perform the spectral calculations for establishing the, *as measured*, encounter-domain spectrum is to implement Eq. (5). This has been shown by [19], and a pseudo code of the implementation is presented in Algorithm 1. Note that, in addition to ship speed, compass heading, transfer function, and directional wave spectrum, the input to the calculations is pre-specified values of both the absolute frequency and the encounter frequency, in the form of vectors ω_0 and ω_e , respectively; and, with both vectors having their elements ordered low to high. On this note, one of the central points in the calculation is that the very starting point is that an absolute frequency is *derived* from a given value of the encounter frequency (as prescribed by the Doppler shift), *not* the other way around. However, since the Doppler shift-obtained absolute frequency is non-discrete, interpolation in the given frequency vector of ω_0 is subsequently necessary. Although it has not been mentioned previously, it should also be noted that the Doppler shift relates (uniquely) *one* encounter frequency to *one* absolute frequency for beam waves as well as for waves forward of beam, and the formula for the conversion is equivalent to Eq. (2a). This is used in line 4 of the pseudo code (Alg. 1). Finally, it should be noted that the pseudo code assumes $U > 0$; stressing that calculations for $U = 0$ are trivial.

Algorithm 1 Pseudo code for computation of response spectrum in encounter domain. Input variables are ship speed, compass heading, transfer function, and directional wave spectrum. A detailed version of the pseudo code is given in [19].

```

1: for index of encounter frequency do
2:   for index of relative wave heading do
3:     if beam waves, or waves forward of beam then
4:       Doppler shift:  $\omega_e \rightarrow \{\omega_0, \frac{d\omega_0}{d\omega_e}\}$ 
5:       Compute response spectrum using Eq. (3a)
6:     else
7:       Doppler shift:  $\omega_e \rightarrow \{\omega_{0,i}, \frac{d\omega_{0,i}}{d\omega_e}\}$  (conditional frequencies and frequency derivatives)
8:       Compute response spectrum using Eq. (5)
9:     end if
10:   end for
11: end for

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4. Case study: Simulated heave motion of a ship

Spectral calculations, using transfer functions in combination with a (directional) wave spectrum, are *theoretical* by default. Consequently, the corresponding ground truth can be produced from consistent time series *simulations* using the exact same set of transfer functions and wave spectrum. This means that *the* best way to assess the performance of the presented (pseudo) algorithm is via a simulation study, where synthetic data of wave-induced responses is simulated, in the time domain, on the one side and compared against the spectral calculation on the other side.

In this study, all simulations address the heave motion of a ship that encounters short-crested waves while advancing in the waves. The ship is characterised by the following main particulars: Length (between perpendiculars) $L_{pp} = 250$ m, breadth (moulded) $B_{mld} = 35.0$ m, draft (design) $T_d = 8.0$ m, and block coefficient $C_B = 0.75$, with the dimensions somewhat arbitrarily set. The ship's heave transfer function has been computed using closed-form expressions [1], which assume a box-shaped vessel and have as input exactly the above-listed main particulars.

4.1 Wave conditions and speed-heading combinations

The seaway is characterised by a directional wave spectrum $E(\omega_0, \nu)$ obtained from a point spectrum $S_\eta(\omega_0)$ overlaid with a spreading function $G(\nu)$ [25]:

$$E(\omega_0, \nu) = S_\eta(\omega_0 | H_s, T_p, \gamma) G(\nu | s, \nu_p) \quad (10)$$

with waves propagating *from* the compass direction ν . In this study, the point spectrum is taken as a generalised JONSWAP wave spectrum, and we use a cosine-2s spreading function with waves spread to 90° on each side of the main direction ν_p . Formulas for the generalised JONSWAP spectrum and the spreading function $G(\nu | s, \nu_p)$ are given by [25]; for completeness, the formulas are presented in Appendix A. The input parameters are H_s (significant wave height), T_p (spectral peak period), γ (peakedness parameter), and s (spreading parameter). The values of the wave parameters are somewhat arbitrarily set to: $H_s = 3.0$ m, $T_p = 11.0$ s, $\gamma = 1.4$, and $s = 4$, and it is assumed that the main wave direction, from which the waves propagate *from*, in all scenarios is $\nu_p = 0^\circ$ (North). In the investigations, the (compass) heading of the ship takes values $\chi = \{150^\circ, 30^\circ\}$, and two different speeds are studied, $U = \{12 \text{ knots}, 24 \text{ knots}\}$. Accordingly, in total, four different scenarios are considered, obtained as $(U, \tilde{\beta})$ -combinations of:

$$U = \{12 \text{ knots}, 24 \text{ knots}\} \quad (11)$$

$$\tilde{\beta} = \{30^\circ, 150^\circ\} \quad (12)$$

where $\tilde{\beta}$ indicates a *main* relative wave heading.

Figure 4: Wave spectrum (left-hand side axis) shown together with magnitudes of the heave transfer function (right-hand side axis). Note that the (*absolute*) frequency is in Hertz, i.e., $f_0 = \frac{\omega_0}{2\pi}$. Ship speed is $U = 24$ knots.

Figure 4 shows the input point wave spectrum together with the magnitude (modulus) of the ship's heave transfer function for some selected relative wave headings; the forward speed is $U = 24$ knots. The immediate observation is that the input wave spectrum overlaps the transfer function with varying degree, depending on the relative wave heading; however, heave motion will be induced for both of the considered *main* relative wave headings ($\tilde{\beta} = 30^\circ$ and $\tilde{\beta} = 150^\circ$), reminding that multi-directional, short-crested waves are considered. The corresponding plot, applicable to ship speed $U = 12$ knots, is included in Appendix B.

4.2 Settings of spectral calculation

The listed combinations of speed and relative wave heading help determine the upper cut-off frequencies for both f_0 and f_e to achieve accurate results doing the spectral calculation; here, recall that the encounter frequency is the starting point of the spectral calculation. Figure 5 shows the Doppler shifts of corresponding absolute and encounter frequencies together with the input wave spectrum; note that ship speed is $U = 24$ knots². For the wave system, having $T_p = 11.0$ s, the energy density has (virtually) dropped to zero for $f_0 = 0.35$ Hz and above. Using $f_0^* \equiv 0.35$ Hz as the cut-off frequency, the corresponding cut-off *encounter* frequency must be $f_e \approx 1.3$ Hz for the speed $U = 24$ knots to *not* discard wave components contributing to a significant degree. On the contrary, had $f_e \equiv 0.35$ Hz been set, it would have led to the removal of a substantial amount of energy for some speed and wave heading combinations, cf. Figure 5. By and large, setting the upper cut-off *encounter* frequency from a compromise between computational speed and accuracy for the specific combinations of vessel speed and relative wave heading, cf. Eqs. (11) and (12), the following values for the cut-off absolute and encounter frequencies are adopted:

$$f_0^* = 0.35 \text{ Hz} \quad (13)$$

$$f_e^* = 1.0 \text{ Hz} \quad (14)$$

We note that a different (i.e., lower) cut-off encounter frequency could be set for the lower forward speed ($U = 12$ knots), but this is not considered.

The spectral calculations are made with different resolutions of the frequency vectors (f_e and f_0) and the wave direction (ν), and the specific settings will appear from the presented results to be discussed later.

Figure 5: Wave spectrum shown together with the Doppler shift ("D.shift") for the speed $U = 24$ knots. Note: The wave spectrum uses the left-hand side axis, while the encounter frequency uses the right-hand side axis.

The above considerations with respect to the cut-off frequency were solely governed by the appearance of the wave spectrum. In practice, however, one should also include the behaviour of the transfer functions. Thus, for a given ship, when the transfer functions, all of those considered in the particular analysis, have effectively gone to zero, there is no interest in wave energy at frequencies higher than the frequency at which the transfer functions are zero. This point has been neglected here for convenience.

²The corresponding plot, applicable to $U = 12$ knots, is included in Appendix B.

Table 1: The effect of resolution on the spectral calculation is tested via six different combinations of the spacing in the frequency and direction vectors.

Resolution	A	B	C	D	E	F
Δf_e [Hz]	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.001	0.001	0.001
Δf_0 [Hz]	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.001	0.001	0.001
$\Delta \nu$ [°]	10	5	1	5	1	0.001

4.3 Settings of time domain simulations and their transformation to frequency domain

In the time series simulations, the absolute frequency vector has $N = 2000$ elements non-equidistantly distributed on the interval [0-0.35] Hz, ensuring that the signal (time series) is without repetition. The wave direction (thus also the relative wave heading) has an equidistant spacing of 0.1° on the full circle $[0^\circ - 360^\circ]$, i.e. $L = 3600$, refer to Subsection 2.3. The time series are sampled at a rate of $f_s = 2$ Hz, with a duration of 2 hours, and 100 realisations are made for each combination of speed and relative wave heading, cf. Eqs. (11) and (12), to ensure statistically representative results. We note that, in reality, measurements must be sampled at a (much) higher rate to avoid aliasing, and to ensure that physical phenomena are fully captured, like hydro-elastic hull girder vibrations if stresses are measured. Furthermore, artificial noise is *not* added to (potentially) allow the corresponding spectral calculation via the developed algorithm [19] to be a perfect match. The transformation of the single time series realisation to frequency domain is made via the estimated auto-covariance function including subsequent smoothing using a Parzen window function [26], thus achieving a spectrum spaced with a $5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ Hz resolution up to 1.0 Hz. Finally, the average spectrum (frequency-wise), denoted by $\hat{R}^t(\omega_e)$, is calculated from all 100 realisations.

Note that the maximum frequency of the obtained spectrum is determined by the Nyquist frequency ($f_N \equiv f_s/2$), which means that information about the frequency content of the realisations is available up to 1.0 Hz; frequencies higher than 1.0 Hz will be subject to aliasing. In other words, the single time series does indeed carry information (i.e., energy) derived from all absolute frequencies up to $f_0^* = 0.35$ Hz in the sampled (temporal) points, which are spaced by $\Delta t = 0.5$ seconds, but any corresponding spectrum will inform about the energy density at (encounter) frequency components just up to $f_N = \frac{1}{2\Delta t} = 1$ Hz. Along the same lines, it is important not to confuse the (real) cut-off frequency f_e^* , introduced in the spectral calculation as Eq. (14), with the maximum frequency of the spectrum computed from the time series, although their values, coincidentally, in this specific case are identical.

5. Results and discussions

In the following, the spectral calculation, refer to Alg. 1 and/or [19], is tested for its performance, and the influence of the resolution of frequency and direction vectors on the obtained results is investigated. Six different sets of resolutions will be studied, see Table 1, and, for any set, the corresponding spectrum $R(\omega_e)$, obtained via the spectral calculation, is computed for every combination of speed and relative wave heading. Altogether, this leads to $(2 \cdot 2) \cdot 6 = 24$ individual cases, and, for every case, a quantitative comparison with the spectrum $\hat{R}^t(\omega_e)$, derived from the time series analysis, is made using the normalised integrated absolute error (NIAE):

$$\text{NIAE} = \frac{1}{m_0} \int_0^\infty \left| R(\omega_e) - \hat{R}^t(\omega_e) \right| d\omega_e \quad (15)$$

It is stressed that the resolution of $\hat{R}^t(\omega_e)$ is the same for all four combinations of speed and relative wave heading. Thus, the calculation of Eqs. (15) requires identical resolution of $R(\omega_e)$ and $\hat{R}^t(\omega_e)$, which is achieved by ("post-processed") linear interpolation, using $\mathbf{f}_e^{ip} = (0.0010 : 5 \cdot 10^{-5} : 1.0000)$ Hz, in $R(\omega_e)$. It should be noted that NIAE is a measure of the detailed (dis)agreement, accumulated frequency by frequency, between the two spectra.

Comparison plots of encounter-response spectra, considering resolutions A-F, are shown in Figures 6-11 for speeds $U = 12$ knots (left-side plots) and $U = 24$ knots (right-side plots), respectively. In addition to the spectra, each graph presents the value of the error measure NIAE.

Evidently, the algorithm performs well but, as reflected by Figure 11, it takes a relatively high resolution in the spectral calculation to obtain a *really* perfect match with the ground truth, i.e., the spectrum derived from the time series simulation. Moreover, it is interesting to note the spurious (nonphysical) oscillations occurring for resolutions D, in particular, but also partly for resolution E. The occurrence (or absence) of the oscillations is due to the Doppler shift's effect when using discrete vectors of frequencies and relative wave heading. The explanation is that, in certain conditions, i.e., for given encounter frequency, speed, and relative wave heading, the corresponding *true* absolute frequency, resulting from the Doppler shift, is "falsely" obtained if the resolution of the relative wave heading vector is too low compared to the resolutions of the frequency vectors. In other words, the nonphysical oscillations are a matter of a mismatch between the true *corresponding* absolute frequency and the actual frequency obtained by interpolation in the discrete vector of the absolute frequency. Another specific remark relates to the observation of the single oscillation occurring at the frequency $f_e \approx 0.03$ Hz for $U = 24$ knots when $\hat{\beta} = 30^\circ$. Although the behaviour reminds of the presence of a singularity, it is not. The single oscillation is resulting from the existence of a cancellation frequency in the heave transfer function(s) around the *absolute* frequency $f_0 = 0.08$ Hz for following and stern-quartering waves, see Figure 4. Indeed, it is observed that the spectral calculation captures the behaviour perfectly when the resolution is high enough, cf. Figure 11.

A condensed quantification of the performance of the spectral calculation is seen by the bar chart of NIAE, see Figure 12. The figure confirms that resolution F achieves the lowest values of NIAE for all speed-heading combinations considered. On the other hand, there is a significant difference in the CPU time required for completing the spectral calculations when using the different sets of resolution, cf. Table 1. For resolution A, the average CPU time³ to complete the calculation for any speed-heading combination is less than one-hundredth of a second, and for resolutions B to E, the CPU time is about a hundredth of a second. However, resolution F requires on the order of 20-25 seconds to complete the spectrum calculation. Depending on the application, it may be of little concern to use a (very) fine resolution, thus securing spectral calculations that perfectly match corresponding time domain simulations or measurements; here assuming the availability of a reliable wave spectrum as well as transfer functions. On the other hand, in applications where iterations are needed, for instance, in wave spectrum estimation using transfer function-dependent frameworks of the wave buoy analogy, a refined resolution can be prohibitive because of high computational costs [27]. Consequently, the resolution must be set according to a compromise; where sensitivity studies in the specific situation can provide general guidelines.

As pointed out in the introduction, spectral calculations using transfer functions and (idealised) wave spectra are theoretical by default. In this sense, the presented case study provides a complete assessment of the procedure [19] devised for doing spectral calculations of wave-induced ship responses. Thus, it is understood that *no* other test cases with alternative idealised wave conditions and other sets of transfer functions are needed; the performance of the procedure will be exactly the same, as the procedure's performance is independent of wave spectrum as well as the response being investigated.

³Calculations performed on a PC with a 13th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-1365U 1.80 GHz processor.

Figure 6: Comparison of encounter spectra; spectral calculation based on **resolution A**. Left-side plots apply to $U = 12$ knots and right-side plots to $U = 24$ knots. Note the difference in the ranges on the y -axes.

Figure 7: Comparison of encounter spectra; spectral calculation based on **resolution B**. Left-side plots apply to $U = 12$ knots and right-side plots to $U = 24$ knots. Note the difference in the ranges on the y -axes.

Figure 8: Comparison of encounter spectra; spectral calculation based on **resolution C**. Left-side plots apply to $U = 12$ knots and right-side plots to $U = 24$ knots. Note the difference in the ranges on the y -axes.

Figure 9: Comparison of encounter spectra; spectral calculation based on **resolution D**. Left-side plots apply to $U = 12$ knots and right-side plots to $U = 24$ knots. Note the difference in the ranges on the y -axes.

Figure 10: Comparison of encounter spectra; spectral calculation based on **resolution E**. Left-side plots apply to $U = 12$ knots and right-side plots to $U = 24$ knots. Note the difference in the ranges on the y -axes.

Figure 11: Comparison of encounter spectra; spectral calculation based on **resolution F**. Left-side plots apply to $U = 12$ knots and right-side plots to $U = 24$ knots. Note the difference in the ranges on the y -axes.

Figure 12: The normalised integrated error (NIAE) for $U = 12$ knots (left-hand side) and $U = 24$ knots (right-hand side), and the dependency on the resolution.

6. Final remarks

Spectral calculations, using a wave spectrum together with transfer functions, offer a fast and reliable means to obtain wave-induced responses of a ship in a seaway. However, the calculations are delicate, in a practical sense, due to the Doppler shift resulting in a 1-to-3 mapping of encounter frequency to absolute frequency in certain conditions when the ship is sailing in waves from abaft beam. In this study, a recipe was devised through a detailed numerical algorithm, refer to [19], for how to make the calculations for a ship sailing at non-zero forward speed meeting waves at any direction considering short-crested, multi-directional wave systems. The study investigated *and* validated the presented (spectral) procedure by comparing obtained results to corresponding ones derived from time series simulations representing a ground truth. It was shown that a perfect match (from an engineering point of view) can be obtained, however, conditional on the resolution of vectors of frequencies and relative wave heading.

Some applications demand (very) low computation time and/or rely on iterative algorithms which make consistent inclusion of the (true) Doppler shift impractical, not to say impossible. In these circumstances, approximating the Doppler shift with a unique (1-to-1) relationship between the absolute and encounter frequencies appears attractive. Research in this direction is ongoing [28], and initial results have been presented in [29].

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A Formulas for idealised directional wave spectrum

The generalised JONSWAP spectrum $S_\eta(\omega_0)$ is given by,

$$S_\eta(\omega_0) = \alpha S(\omega_0), \quad (16a)$$

$$S(\omega_0) = \frac{g^2}{\omega_0^5} \exp \left[-\frac{5}{4} \left(\frac{\omega_p}{\omega_0} \right)^4 \right] \gamma^r, \quad (16b)$$

$$r = \exp \left[-\frac{(\omega_0 - \omega_p)^2}{2\sigma^2 \omega_p^2} \right], \quad (16c)$$

$$\alpha = \frac{H_s^2}{16} \frac{1}{\int_0^\infty S(\omega_0) d\omega_0} \quad (16d)$$

where the peak frequency $\omega_p = \frac{2\pi}{T_p}$, and

$$\sigma = \begin{cases} 0.07 & \omega_0 \leq \omega_p \\ 0.09 & \omega_0 > \omega_p \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

Note that the normalisation, in terms of multiplication by α , cf. Eq. (16d), ensures that $H_s \equiv 4\sqrt{\int S_\eta(\omega_0) d\omega_0}$ when Eq. (16a) is integrated numerically.

The spreading function $G(\nu)$ is defined by,

$$G^*(\nu|s, \nu_p) = A(s) \cdot \cos^{2s} \left(\frac{\nu - \nu_p}{2} \right), \quad \nu_p - 90^\circ \leq \nu \leq \nu_p + 90^\circ \quad (18a)$$

$$A(s) = \frac{2^{2s-1} \Gamma^2(s+1)}{\pi \Gamma(2s+1)} \quad (18b)$$

$$G(\nu) = \frac{G^*(\nu|s, \nu_p)}{\int_{\nu_p-90^\circ}^{\nu_p+90^\circ} G^*(\nu|s, \nu_p) d\nu} \quad (18c)$$

where Γ denotes the Gamma function. The normalisation in Eq. (18c) is made to ensure that $\int G(\nu) d\nu = 1$.

B Transfer functions and Doppler shift for ship speed 12 knots

Figure 13: Wave spectrum (left-hand side axis) shown together with magnitudes of the heave transfer function (right-hand side axis). Note that the (*absolute*) frequency is in Hertz, i.e., $f_0 = \frac{\omega_0}{2\pi}$. Ship speed is $U = 12$ knots.

Figure 14: Wave spectrum shown together with the Doppler shift ("D.shift") for the speed $U = 12$ knots. Note: The wave spectrum uses the left-hand side axis, while the encounter frequency uses the right-hand side axis.